

Title: Exploring the relevance and applicability of the irecs training materials on emerging technologies for diverse cultural and regulatory contexts through reflective interviews

1.Contributors

Table 1: Contributions table according to CRediT (Contribution Roles Taxonomy) author statement

Task	Definition	Contributor
Conceptualisation	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	Claudia Pallise Perello, Giulia Inguaggiato, Susan Berentsen, Natalie Evans, Mariette van den Hoven
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	Claudia Pallise Perello, Giulia Inguaggiato, Susan Berentsen, Natalie Evans, Mariette van den Hoven
Investigation – Data collection	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	Claudia Pallise Perello, Giulia Inguaggiato, Susan Berentsen, Mariette van den Hoven
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data	Claudia Pallise Perello, Giulia Inguaggiato
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	Claudia Pallise Perello
Writing – Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or postpublication stages	All

2. Introduction

Background:

The irecs (Improving Research Ethics expertise and Competencies to ensure reliability and trust in Science) project aims to design, develop and implement sustainable training materials on research ethics focused on emerging technologies including biobanking, artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare, gene editing, and extended reality. These training materials are designed to be used by trainers to teach diverse stakeholder groups, including students, researchers, and research ethics experts. The scope of the project is global, therefore materials will need to be suitable to be used in a wide range of diverse settings.

To foster the successful implementation of the training around the globe, it is important to understand the appropriateness of the irecs materials for diverse cultural, social, and regulatory contexts, and to understand how materials can be adapted for specific contexts. Some studies have already highlighted that taking into account the context in which ethics training will take place is a key factor in the design (ensuring its relevance) and implementation (ensuring its applicability) of ethics training (Bagdasarov et al., 2012; Watts et al., 2017). We define *relevance* as the extent to which the content of training materials address the specific ethical issues, values, and perspectives of local contexts. *Applicability*, on the other hand, refers to the extent to which the materials can be practically implemented and meaningfully used in different settings, considering factors such as institutional infrastructure, regulatory requirements, and local pedagogical practices.

Existing evaluations of research ethics training have revealed the importance of the cultural adaptation of ethics training to enhance the perceived relevance, self-reported effectiveness and applicability of implementation. For instance, the mix-methods study by Pearson et al. (2014) evaluating the adaptation of an ethics training module for American Indian and Alaska Native community researchers, shows that participants who followed a culturally adapted module, compared to those who followed a standard version, reported higher scores on relevance of materials and higher self-efficacy. Additionally, the qualitative study by Pratt et al. (2014), based on interviews to research ethics trainers and trainees of different countries of the Pacific using the same research ethics training, highlights challenges in applying Western bioethical principles in non-Western contexts. This study, provides examples of successful adaptation of research ethics training, such as including non-Western principles and theories or incorporating region-specific case studies (Pratt et al., 2014). Thus, context adaptation of ethics training modules can improve the relevance and applicability across diverse settings, highlighting the importance of tailoring materials to local contexts for more impactful and inclusive training materials.

Furthermore, in all research collaborations, there is a risk that authority and knowledge production are disproportionately shaped by the more powerful parties, leading to epistemic hierarchies and consequent epistemic injustices. In particular, we acknowledge that materials developed in specific European settings may contain gaps (i.e., conceptual gaps) that contribute to epistemic injustices and make it difficult for individuals in different contexts (such as trainers and students) to fully engage, relate to, and apply the content of the training. Epistemic injustices, as described by Fricker (2007, p. 7), arise when certain populations are wronged in their capacity of knowers in their capacity as knowers, either

through systemic marginalization from knowledge production or due to gaps in the collective social knowledge needed to interpret their own experiences. In the context of research ethics training, these injustices can lead to collective and individual impoverishment of training materials, affecting their applicability and relevance across different social and geographical contexts. Overcoming these injustices requires actively reflecting on and addressing missing conceptual resources to make knowledge more inclusive and representative of diverse realities (Furst, 2024). Since the irecs project is a research project based on international collaborations, it is crucial to critically examine the risk of epistemic injustices that could affect the relevance and acceptability of the project's training materials in diverse settings.

With this study, we aim to investigate the applicability and relevance of the irecs material and see if there are any gaps or obstacles that might make the irecs materials less effective and contribute to epistemic injustices. To this purpose, reflective will be conducted, covering a wide field of European and non-European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

Research Question: What is the relevance and applicability of training materials on emergent research ethics challenges in diverse social, cultural, and regulatory contexts?

Objectives:

- To explore the relevance and applicability of the irecs materials on emergent technologies in diverse teaching contexts.
- To compare the perspectives on the applicability and relevance of the materials of participants from different cultural, social, and regulatory contexts.
- To identify potential conceptual gaps
- To describe possible adaptations to the materials to make them more relevant and applicable in diverse contexts.

Theoretical Background:

The study adopts an socio-cultural constructivist approach to research ethics training, recognizing that the applicability and relevance training materials depend and are highly influenced by local cultural norms, regulatory frameworks, and social values.

3. Methods

3.1 Design

This is a qualitative study that will use reflective interviews to explore the perspectives of participants on the irecs materials in regard to their diverse contexts. Reflective interviews are a qualitative method that uses research interviews as an intervention tool that can potentially impact the research participant, the researcher, a material or all (Nardon et al., 2021). This method has been selected since it aims to facilitate both participants' and researcher's reflection with the aim of achieving impact. In the case of irecs materials, this method's pace for reflection, inquiry and practice, makes it relevant for us to discover the contextually specific relevance and applicability of the irecs modules, due to its reflective nature and iterative and co-constructivist process (Nardon et al., 2021; Rogers et al., 2024).

In this study we will use an adaptation of the approach to reflective interviewing proposed by Nardon et al. (2021, p. 5). Their framework establishes that reflective interviewing has four components (1) giving respondents time to think (2) developing a trusting relationship (3) inviting reflection and (4) supporting the identification of a solution. These components do not need to be in this specific order, since interviewing is an iterative process that should be adapted to each specific participant, topic, etc.

The interview guide (Appendix 1) will be piloted with an ethics researcher prior to the start of the interviews with participants using the “Thinking-out-loud method”, which asks participants to share their perceptions and thoughts while performing an assigned task, in this case, reading the interview questions. The structure and questions of the interview guide will be adapted according to this pilot.

3.2 Participants

Selection of participants will be done using the survey that trainers responded to pre-and post irecs train-the-trainer event. We will use a strategy of purposive sampling.

- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Participants that have participated in one of the irecs train-the-trainer sessions, and have a good understanding and overview of the materials and ways of implementing those.
 - Availability and consent to participate in a one hour interview.
 - Able to do the interview in English

- **Diversity of the sample:**
 - Participants need to represent various cultural, social, and regulatory contexts. Ideally, they must represent countries with well established ethics regulations and governance regarding new technologies, countries that have regulations but not up-to-date to new technologies, and countries that lack national ethical governance and regulations regarding new technologies. Must represent European and non-European parties.
 - Participants that aim to train different stakeholder groups (students, researchers or research ethics experts).
 - Diversity in gender.
 - Diversity in professional seniority.

3.3 Data Collection

Each participant will be invited to a maximum 1-hour interview via Microsoft Teams, with video and audio recording after consent. Interviews will be semi-structured (interview guide appendix I) and participants will be encouraged to self-reflect and think out-loud while reviewing some selected short excerpts of the irecs materials.

Moreover, each participant will be sent a short questionnaire on demographic information including: gender, seniority, country of affiliated institution.

3.4. Analysis

Interviews will be transcribed automatically and transcriptions will be checked by CPP. After transcription, interviews will be analysed using a thematic approach. Transcripts will be uploaded to MAXQDA software and coded line-by-line and following an inductive coding. Developed codes will be discussed by all authors after the coding of 5 interviews. These codes will be modified and specified. The rest of the interviews will be coded using that coding tree, which will be open to modifications in the coding process. Discussion of disagreements and specifications will take place regularly.

3.5. Ethics Approval

The study protocol (reference 2024.0848) was fully reviewed by the non-WMO Committee of the Medical Ethics Review Committee of Amsterdam University Medical Centers (FWA00032965) which provided confirmation that the study does not fall under the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO).

References:

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Appendix 1: Interview guide

1. Building trust:

- Intro:
 - a. Welcome and explain the purpose of the session
 - b. Obtain consent
 - c. Highlight the reflective nature of the interview and emphasize the value of the participant's perspective, and the aim to generate impact on the materials
- Understanding the context of the participant:
 - a. Can you describe your role as a trainer and briefly explain what is your experience in training research ethics, if any?

2. Inviting reflection:

- First impressions of the irecs materials:
 - a. Can you think about three words that come to mind when you think about the modules?
 - b. What is the most useful and relevant element/aspect in the modules?
 - c. Can the materials be applied in your institutional context? (brief answer)
- Deeper reflection - gaps:
 - a. Are there any topics or concepts that you think are missing or underrepresented in the module and which could be of particular value to you as a trainer in your context? - if needed, give examples
 - b. Are there concepts/topics that are difficult to transfer in your context (for example due to cultural, regulatory or linguistic differences)? - if needed, give examples.
 - c. Do you feel that the materials represent a particular cultural or ethical framework/perspective? If so, how?

3. Giving time to think:

- Show a SELECTED excerpt of the materials:
 - a. Biobanking module, social justice module, case study on gene editing/AI
- Wait a couple of minutes, so participants can reflect on the materials and then ask:
 - a. What thoughts or reactions come to mind after reading/watching this?
 - b. Is this material relevant for your context?
 - c. Is this applicable in your context? / Could/would you use this material in your teaching/context?

4. Supporting the identification of solution:

- Implementation - personal:
 - a. Going back to the irecs materials in general: Can you think about specific modifications that would improve the applicability of the modules in your specific setting? (ask for examples)
 - b. How do you imagine using the materials in your specific setting? (give examples: lecture, group discussion, online meeting, etc.)
 - c. *Is there anything you need to use these materials in practice?*
- *Do you foresee any challenges in using the material in your own teaching/context?*

- Implementation - general:
 - a. To what extent are these materials relevant for trainees from different backgrounds?
 - b. What changes would you make to the irecs materials, for them to be relevant and applicable for different contexts?

5. Closing and final reflection

- Is there anything else you want to share with us?
- How did you experience reflecting on the materials? Did this interview impact in any way your perspective?
- Thank and explain next steps of the study